

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PERSONALITY FACTORS BETWEEN SPORTSPERSONS OF CONTACT AND NON-CONTACT SPORTS

Gulzar Ahmad Rathar¹,

Jigmat Dachen²

¹Research Scholar, Bhagwant University,
Ajmer, Rajasthan, India

²Assistant Professor,
Directorate of Physical Education & Sports,
University of Kashmir,
Srinagar, Jammu and Kashmir, India

Abstract:

The main purpose of the present study was to compare the personality factors between the sportspersons of the contact and non-contact sports. Big five personality inventory was employed among the sportsperson selecting randomly from colleges of Ganderbal Kashmir region. The size of sample under study was 70, in which 26 were from contact sports (football, hockey, kabaddi, basketball, handball and rugby) and 44 were from non-contact sports (cricket, volleyball, badminton, baseball, ball badminton and shooting ball). The groups were compared on different factors of personality i.e, extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism and openness. The results show almost same personality characteristics exist between the sportspersons of contact and non-contact sports, since calculated 't' values of 0.76 (extraversion), 0.31 (agreeableness), 1.05 (conscientiousness), 0.05 (neuroticism) and 1.1 (openness) for five personality factors were not found statistically significant ($p \leq 0.05$).

Keywords: personality, contact, non-contact sports

1. Introduction

Personality is defined as a prediction of what a person can do in a given situation. The crux of sports performance is dependent upon the personality makeup of an individual. It has been proved by different researches that a good performance only comes after a person attains a well-balanced personality. The personality assessments among sportspersons become very popular in 1960s, in which hundreds of articles were published mainly focusing on relationship between personality and sports performance. But in recent past very limited studies are focus on personality as very

weak evidences were found as far as personality and sports performance are concerned, but we can't altogether ignore the psychic effect on sports performance. Individual possessing certain personality traits are attracted towards sports whereas, some individual don't like sports at all, this phenomena is explain by 'gravitational hypothesis' (Morgan, 1974), Morgan believed that individual who possess stable, extraverted personalities are generally attracted toward certain sports. It is well established fact that personality factors of sportspersons are distinctly different from general norm (Morgan 1980), the literature shows that sportspersons in one sport often differ in personality type and profile from sportspersons in other sports (Franken, Hill & Kierstead, 1994). Moreover, there are personality differences exist between the sportspersons of team sports (e.g, football, rugby etc) and individual sports (body builder, gymnastic, karate participants etc), between the direct and parallel sports, similarly between the sports persons of different skill levels. The numerous studies focus on personality differences are available in the literatures are: Singer (1969); Schuur, Ashley, and Joy (1977); Clingman and Hilliard (1987); Franken, Hill & Kierstead, (1994); Davis & Mogk, (1994); Morgan, (1980) etc. It seems reasonable for example, to expect a sportspersons of contact sports like football, rugby, wrestling and hockey to be more aggressive, anxious and tolerant of pain than a golfer or a tennis player or badminton player. However, it is unreasonable to expect a high correlation between personality factors and sports type. Therefore, in the present study we attempted to compare the personality factors between the sportspersons of contact and non-contact sports on different parameters of big five personality factors.

2. Method and Materials

The purpose of the study was to compare the personality factors between contact and non-contact sportspersons.

2.1 Tools

Structure questionnaire namely Big Five Personality Inventory developed by Goldberg in 1993 was used as tool for the purpose of collecting data on personality factor. Big five personality inventory is a widely used tool to access the personality makeup of sports persons regarding the field of games and sports. The Big Five personality questionnaire consist of five universal personality factors namely; extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism and openness which comprise of 44 items.

2.2 Participants

The participants for the present study were selected randomly from Government College of Physical Education, Ganderbal, Kashmir and Government Degree College Ganderbal, Kashmir. The participants consist of 26 contact sportspersons and 44 non-contact sports persons. Sportsperson who participated in football, hockey, kabaddi, basketball, handball and rugby were grouped into contact sports and those participate

in cricket, volleyball, badminton, baseball, ball badminton and shooting ball were grouped into non-contact sports. At the time of collecting data, the respondents were fully instructed and all the 44 items of the questionnaire were verbally dictated up to the understanding levels of every respondent and then the respondents solved the questionnaire by their own. After scoring with the help of keys, the data was analysis with the help of statistical package (SPSS). The results were established and then put in a tabular form and the mean difference was calculated to find out the significant difference in personality between contact and non-contact sportsperson with the help of the 't'-test.

3. Results and Discussions

After interpreting, the collected data two tables (Table 1 & 2) are generated to display the descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) to describe the nature of data and compare the groups on personality factors.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Personality Factors among the Sportspersons Contact and Non-contact Sports

Personality factors	Sports	N	Mean	S.D	Std. error mean
Extroversion	Contact Sports	26	27.61	3.49	.68
	Non-Contact Sports	44	26.84	4.44	.66
Agreeableness	Contact Sports	26	33.69	5.28	1.03
	Non-Contact Sports	44	34.06	4.66	.70
Conscientiousness	Contact Sports	26	32.42	3.98	.78
	Non-Contact Sports	44	33.54	4.50	.67
Neuroticism	Contact Sports	26	21.69	4.05	.79
	Non-Contact Sports	44	21.75	4.47	.67
Openness	Contact Sports	26	34.30	4.09	.80
	Non-Contact Sports	44	35.59	4.85	.73

The Table 1 shows that the mean, standard deviation and standard error of mean are normal and data is normally distributed which is importance for the application of parametric statistics like 't' Test.

Table 2: Independent sample 't' test on Personality Factors between contact and non-contact sportsperson

Variables	't' Value	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Std. error difference
Extroversion	0.76	68	0.45	0.77	1.01
Agreeableness	0.31	68	0.75	0.37	1.21
Conscientiousness	1.05	68	0.29	1.12	1.66
Neuroticism	0.05	68	0.95	0.05	1.06
Openness	1.13	68	0.26	1.2	1.13

The result of the independent 't' test results shows that none of the factor is significant when compare between the sportspersons of contact and non-contact sports.

Figure 1: Graphical representation of difference between contact and non-contact sportspersons on personality factors

In this study the main concern was to study the overall personality patterns of the sports persons for that Big Five Inventory was used to check and compare the personality on different patterns of personality like, openness, neuroticism, extroversion, conscientiousness and agreeableness whereas, it is found that no differences exist between the two groups. The earlier studies conducted on comparison of personalities on national and Olympic level athletes show significant differences on level of extroversion and neuroticism, openness and conscientiousness. Some other studies in this field also show some differences in parameters due to the influence of express at different competitive levels. Unlike previous studies which compare personality between sportsperson and non-sports persons, between individual and team sports, in the present study there is no significant difference in personality between contact and non-contact sportspersons.

4. Conclusions

Since personality is multifaceted and complex, so need multivariate approach of statistics, moreover, the subjects in the present study were inter-collegiate level athletes, whereas, in previous studies the subjects were national level or elite level sportspersons. Hence, this study couldn't able to find significant difference in personality factors between the sportspersons of contact and non-contact sports. It is also believed that regular participation in sports can enhance personality development. Tattersfield (1971) has provided longitudinal evidence that athletic participation develop personality. Sports performances and personality inbuilt are the two sides of the same coin as one cannot predict success unless he/she is personally balanced and mentally fit for the given field. Personality plays a vital role in sports achievements, it

includes, emotions, aspirations, feelings, stress, anxiety, fear, anger, love, self-esteem, achievement, motivation and dedication.

References

1. Cillingman, J.M., & Hilliard, D.V. (1987). Some personality characteristics of the super-adherer: Following those who go beyond fitness. *Journal of Sports Behavior*, 10, 123-136.
2. Cox, R. H. (2002). *Sports Psychology: Concepts and application*. McGraw Hill New York.
3. Davis, C., & Mogk, J.P. (1994). Some personality correlates of interest and excellence in sports, *International Journal of Sports Psychology*, 25, 131-143.
4. Franken, R.E., Hill, R., & Kierstead, J. (1994). Sports interest as predicted by the personality measures of competitiveness, mastery, instrumentality, expressivity and sensation seeking. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 17(4),467-476.
5. John, O.P., & Srivastava, S. (1999). The Big-Five trait taxonomy: History, measurement, and theoretical perspectives. In L. A. Pervin & O. P. John (Eds.), *Handbook of personality: Theory and research* (Vol. 2, pp. 102–138). New York: Guilford Press.
6. Morgan, W.P. (1974). Selected psychological considerations in sports. *Research Quarterly*, 45, 32-339.
7. Morgan, W.P. (1980). The trait psychology controversy. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sports*, 51, 50-76.
8. Morris, T. & Summer J. (2004). *Sports Psychology: theory, application and Issues*. John Willey & Sons Australia.
9. Schurr, K.T., Ashley, M.A., & Joy, K.L. (1977). A multivariate analysis of male athlete characteristic: sports type and success. *Multivariate Experimental Clinical Research*, 3, 53-68.
10. Singer (1969). Personality differences between and within baseball and tennis players. *Research Quarterly*, 40, 582-587.
11. Weinberg, R.S., & Gould, D. (1999). *Foundation of sports and exercise psychology*. Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.

Gulzar Ahmad Rathar, Jigmat Dachen
COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PERSONALITY FACTORS BETWEEN SPORTSPERSONS OF
CONTACT AND NON-CONTACT SPORTS

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).